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COMPARATIVE BIOMORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TOMATO CULTIVARS GROWN IN POLYCARBONATE GREENHOUSES IN THE ABSHERON ZONE OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

Agayev F.

*PhD in Biology, Associate Professor, Academician of the International Academy of Agrarian Education
Leading Researcher, Laboratory of Functional Analyses, "Vegetable Growing Research Institute" Public
Legal Entity*

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3366-081

Aliyeva Z.

*PhD in Agricultural Sciences, Associate Professor
Leading Researcher, Department of Greenhouse Vegetable Growing, "Vegetable Growing Research Institute" Public Legal Entity*

ORCID ID: 0009-0002-2055-6981

Gaziyeva G.,

Asadova R.

dr., Senior Researcher, Laboratory of Biologically Active Natural Substances, "Y.H. Mammadaliyev Institute of Petrochemical Processes of the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan"

Baku, Azerbaijan

Baku, Azerbaijan

ORCID ID: 0009-0006-2645-3931

Abstract

In 2023–2024, 42 tomato genotypes cultivated in cocopeat under greenhouse conditions at the "Vegetable Growing Research Institute" public legal entity were evaluated at the technical maturity stage based on certain morphological traits (fruit height, diameter, index, average fresh and dry weight per fruit) and biochemical parameters (dry matter, sugars, extractive substances, total acidity, sugar-to-acid ratio, nitrates). It was determined that in the studied tomato genotypes fruit height ranged from 32.97–64.29 mm, diameter 24.10–71.97 mm, index 0.76–1.50, average fresh and dry weight per fruit 7.41–135.67 g and 0.49–7.73 g, respectively; dry matter content 4.33–7.28%, sugars 1.0–4.28%, extractive substances (soluble in cell sap) 2.73–5.46%, total acidity 0.23–0.51%, sugar-acid ratio 1.96–13.38, nitrate content 56.0–202.9 mg/kg. The wide variation in these indicators among the studied tomato genotypes made it possible to select 10 samples differing in both appearance and biochemical composition, which can be used as valuable initial parental forms in future quality-oriented breeding. Such samples include genotypes 343, 394, 398, 401, 462, A-6 F₁, A-8 F₁, A-12 F₁, A-15 F₁, and A-17 F₁. In these samples, dry matter content was 5.65–7.28%, sugars 2.68–4.28%, extractive substances 4.06–5.46%, total acidity 0.23–0.38%, sugar-acid ratio 7.38–13.38, and nitrate content 56.0–185.6 mg/kg. Four of the selected F₁ hybrids also stood out for their lowest nitrate content (56.0–90.1 mg/kg), which is 3.33–5.36 times lower than the maximum permissible level (300 mg/kg) set by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan for greenhouse-grown tomatoes. Therefore, these hybrids can undoubtedly serve as valuable initial donors in breeding programs aimed at producing environmentally safe products.

Keywords: tomato genotypes, biomorphological indicators, biochemical indicators, breeding, greenhouse.

Introduction. The cultivation of tomatoes in polycarbonate-covered greenhouses has specific characteristics related to creating an optimal microclimate and protecting the plants from diseases. During this cultivation, the optimal temperature for tomato growth should be **+22...+25°C during the day** and **+16...+18°C at night**. The temperature in the greenhouse should not be allowed to rise above **30°C**, as this may cause the anthers to become sterile and the flowers to fail to fertilize. In hot weather, the greenhouse should be ventilated to reduce the temperature; under these conditions, air circulation is not harmful to the plants [Balashov E.S., 2006]. In polycarbonate-covered greenhouses, vents are opened, and the upper part of the greenhouse can be whitened to protect against excessive heat. To ensure rapid evaporation of excess moisture, tomato plants should be irrigated during the first half of the

day. A. Orlov (2021) demonstrated that both high and low temperatures negatively affect tomato plants under greenhouse conditions. When the temperature decreases to 13–15°C, flower buds do not open and fertilized ovaries drop, while at 10°C plant growth ceases. At 5°C, flowers and fruits are destroyed. Light frosts are lethal for tomato plants. Similarly, when the temperature rises above 32°C, pollen grains do not germinate, photosynthesis is weakened, and fruits become pale. Under low light levels, tomato plants elongate, stems thin, leaves become small, and the flower cluster forms above the 10th leaf. The critical light intensity is considered to be 2000–3000 lx, at which point the consumption of plastic substances in respiration exceeds the production from photosynthesis. For normal formation of generative organs, the light intensity should not be below 4000–6000 lx.

N.M. Pus and N.A. Snezkov (2021) found that when cultivating tomatoes on inert substrates in winter greenhouses using innovative agricultural methods, the delivery of nutrients to the substrates via drip irrigation promotes the proper development of both the plants' root systems and the plants themselves. They reported that under such cultivation, tomato fruits contained 4.53–4.87% dry matter, 1.35–1.47% sugars, 11.20–15.99 mg/100 g of ascorbic acid, and 7.60–15.56 mg/kg of nitrates. In another study, tomato plants grown under greenhouse conditions exhibited variations in main stem length and leaf number, and a strong correlation was established between these indicators and plant productivity ($r = 0.83\text{--}0.89$) [E.V. Sokolova et al., 2020].

According to the literature, the application of humic fertilizers during the cultivation of vegetables, particularly tomatoes, in covered soil promotes the production of high-quality, environmentally safe products. Koryagin et al. [Yu.V. Koryagin et al., 2020] reported that under such treatment, tomato fruits contained 5.9–7.6% dry matter, 2.0–2.6% sugars, 25.2–26.8 mg/100 g of ascorbic acid, and 0.72–0.75% total acidity. Nitrate content – a toxic substance – ranged from 90 to 103 mg/kg, representing a 6.4–18.2% reduction compared with the control. Overall, depending on the stage of development, tomato fruits typically contain 4.5–15.0% dry matter, 1.0–4.5% sugars, 0.2–0.9% organic acids, and 19–55 mg/100 g of vitamin C (on a fresh weight basis) [Allahverdiyev E.I. et al., 2020; Musin A.K. et al., 2020; Anisimov A.M., 2021]. The content of toxic substances – nitrates – in tomato fruits can vary widely depending on the microclimatic conditions in the greenhouse, as well as on irrigation and fertilization regimes and light intensity. In our studies, nitrate levels in tomato fruits never exceeded the permissible limit set by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan for this greenhouse-grown vegetable (300 mg/kg), with the maximum value recorded at 201.9 mg/kg [Yusifov M.A., Agazade F.N., 2003; Agayev F.N. et al., 2023; Agayev F.N. et al., 2024]. It is known that **nitrates themselves are not harmful to the human body**. The danger arises only from their reduced form **nitrites**. Nitrites readily enter condensation reactions with **secondary amines and amides** present in food, forming **nitrosamines**. Currently, there are over **300 nitrosamines** known to have **carcinogenic effects**. On the other hand, it should be noted that **nitrates are essential substances for the human body**. Their effect on the human organism is **dual in nature** positive, by enhancing the body's defense functions, and negative, by contributing to the development of **oncological diseases** and **methemoglobinemia** [Litvinov S.S. et al., 2014].

Thus, summarizing the above, it can be concluded that under Absheron conditions, tomato genotypes in greenhouse environments have not been sufficiently studied from biomorphological and biochemical perspectives, and highly productive and high-quality varieties and hybrids suitable for greenhouse conditions have not been developed. Our research is conducted specifically to address this gap, making it highly relevant for modern vegetable production in Azerbaijan.

The purpose of the study. The main purpose of the research was to comparatively evaluate tomato genotypes grown in cocovit under greenhouse conditions in Absheron based on their morphological and biochemical characteristics, and to select valuable parental forms for future quality-based breeding.

Object and methodology of the study. The object of the study comprised 42 tomato genotypes. Plant care and biometric measurements were carried out according to generally accepted methodology [Litvinov S.S., 2011]. Irrigation and mineral nutrition were applied using the drip method [Ezaev A.K., Shbizukhov Z.S., 2017].

The total sugar content in the fruits was determined using an RA-130 refractometer (Korea), the content of extractive substances was measured with an RX-5000 CX extractor (ATAGO, Japan), nitrates were measured using a Nitratometer (SOEKS), and the total acidity and dry matter content were determined according to the methodology of A.I. Yermakov [1987].

The **fruit index** was determined using the following formula:

$$J = \frac{H}{D},$$

Here **J** — fruit index, **H** — fruit height, mm; **D** — fruit diameter, mm.

The **statistical analysis of the research results** was carried out according to S.S. Litvinova (2011).

Results and Discussion of the Study. The fruits of **42 tomato genotypes** (2 regional varieties, 1 promising variety, 2 selections, 14 pure lines, and 23 F₁ hybrids) grown in **cocovit under greenhouse conditions** were evaluated at the **technical maturity stage** for certain **morphological** (fruit height, diameter, index, average fresh and dry weight per fruit) and **biochemical** (dry matter, sugars, extractive substances, total acidity, sugar-to-acid ratio, nitrates) characteristics (Tables 1 and 2). It was determined that in the studied samples, **fruit height** ranged from **32.97 to 64.29 mm**, **diameter** from **24.10 to 71.97 mm**, and the **fruit index** from **0.76 to 1.50**. The **average fresh and dry weight per fruit** were **7.41–153.71 g** and **0.49–8.22 g**, respectively. The **dry matter content** in the fruits ranged from **4.33 to 7.28%**, **sugar content** from **1.0 to 4.28%**, **extractive substances** from **2.73 to 5.46%**, **total acidity** (calculated as malic and citric acid) from **0.23 to 0.51%**, the **sugar-to-acid ratio** from **1.96 to 13.38**, and **nitrate content** from **56.0 to 202.9 mg/kg**.

The wide variation of morphological and biochemical traits among genotypes allows for the selection of samples that differ according to the reliability level (LSD₀₅). Statistical analysis of the obtained results [S.S. Litvinov, 2011] showed that the fruit height and diameter were 48.49 ± 5.02 mm and 57.0 ± 6.04 mm, respectively, with LSD₀₅ for these traits being 9.99 mm and 12.02 mm. The fruits differ in height as follows at a 95% confidence level: 398 (64.29 mm), A-17 (32.97 mm), and A-15 (36.08 mm). In terms of diameter, the fruits differ as follows: 394 (71.66 mm), 396 (71.97 mm), A-15 (24.10 mm), and A-17 (33.81 mm). Regarding the fruit index, only A-15 (1.50) differs. The remaining samples fall within the confidence interval. Deviations from the confidence interval for fruit moisture and dry mass are observed in a

larger number of genotypes. Such genotypes include 393 (120.62 and 6.15 g), 394 (130.19 and 8.01 g), 396 (152.71 and 8.22 g), 462 (135.67 and 7.73 g), and A-18 (128.05 and 7.15 g). The remaining samples have fruit moisture and dry mass values within the confidence interval. An interesting point is that all genotypes differing in the upper confidence interval are large-fruited. However, it should be noted that there are also samples

differing in the lower confidence interval. These include A-15 (7.41 and 0.49 g), A-17 (13.12 and 0.96 g), and A-7 (50.27 and 2.55 g).

It should be noted that the majority of the studied tomato genotypes were flat-oval in shape (34 genotypes – 0.76–0.90), only one genotype was elongated (1.50), and seven genotypes were relatively elongated-round in shape (0.91–0.98).

Table 1.

Comparative evaluation of the fruits of tomato genotypes grown in cocopeat under greenhouse conditions according to some biomorphological parameters (average for 2023–2024)

№	Catalog sample of the VGRI	Names of the genotypes	Fruit height, mm	Fruit diameter, mm	Fruit index	Average moisture content per fruit, g	Average dry mass per fruit, g
1	86	Banovsha, registered variety, standard	51,13	63,67	0,80	120,45	5,80
2	138	Shalala, registered variety, standard	42,91	52,61	0,82	63,14	3,88
3	140	Pure line	50,11	61,44	0,82	94,90	4,41
4	283	Pure line	47,77	60,92	0,78	101,85	5,56
5	285	Pure line	46,27	55,77	0,83	87,82	5,48
6	296	Pure line	48,33	60,30	0,81	93,41	5,70
7	306	Pure line	49,40	59,20	0,83	93,45	5,05
8	307	Pure line	43,75	51,20	0,86	60,94	3,28
9	321	Pure line	45,26	56,74	0,80	68,13	3,77
10	343	Pure line	48,64	64,24	0,76	74,45	4,45
11	356	Pure line	48,14	62,32	0,77	101,21	5,70
12	393	Pure line	53,66	65,06	0,83	120,62	6,15
13	394	Sample selected from the variety Atlas	55,63	71,66	0,78	130,19	8,01
14	395	Pure line (New variety)	49,38	56,88	0,87	86,52	4,61
15	396	Pure line	64,29	71,97	0,89	152,71	8,22
16	398	Sample selected from the variety First Ladu	47,19	53,57	0,88	62,10	3,62
17	401	Pure line	46,37	52,62	0,83	62,43	3,67
18	415	Pure line	45,75	58,17	0,79	62,89	3,29
19	417	Pure line	43,70	56,74	0,80	74,45	3,93
20	462	Mulmuctap F ₁	54,22	65,63	0,83	135,67	7,73
21	A-1	(43x420) F ₁	49,05	63,10	0,78	109,70	5,34
22	A-2	(495x391) F ₁	50,64	56,45	0,90	78,61	4,11
23	A-3	(436x415) F ₁	52,41	58,94	0,89	92,14	4,88
24	A-5	(306x285) F ₁	42,30	50,85	0,83	59,10	3,36
25	A-6	(475x468) F ₁	49,78	53,54	0,93	72,92	4,18
26	A-7	(138x283) F ₁	40,86	47,97	0,85	50,27	2,55
27	A-8	(375x436) F ₁	52,66	56,45	0,93	81,12	4,93
28	A-9	(198x306) F ₁	49,81	57,31	0,87	87,85	4,88
29	A-10	(198x307) F ₁	45,16	49,99	0,90	59,36	3,08
30	A-12	(420x415) F ₁	48,50	60,55	0,80	93,81	5,30
31	A-14	(306x283) F ₁	47,62	54,63	0,87	77,11	3,97
32	A-15	(351x447) F ₁	36,08	24,10	1,50	7,41	0,49
33	A-17	(584x351) F ₁	32,97	33,81	0,98	13,12	0,96

34	A-18	(487x395) F ₁	53,41	66,09	0,81	128,05	7,15
35	A-20	(468x420) F ₁	52,32	54,77	0,96	81,61	3,94
36	A-24	(487x321) F ₁	54,94	64,95	0,85	102,38	5,76
37	A-25	(487x143) F ₁	49,74	53,44	0,93	78,90	3,97
38	A-26	(375x425) F ₁	47,44	59,85	0,90	75,86	3,97
39	A-27	(307x283) F ₁	45,82	50,13	0,91	60,28	3,04
40	A-28	(307x306) F ₁	50,76	55,95	0,91	77,66	4,03
41	A-29	(468x438) F ₁	54,89	61,70	0,89	108,96	4,72
42	A-30	(391x143) F ₁	47,63	58,78	0,81	86,13	4,16
Range of variation			32,97-64,29	24,10-71,97	0,76-1,50	7,41-152,71	0,49-8,22 q
$\bar{X} \pm S_{\bar{x}}$			48,49±5,02	57,0±6,04	0,89±0,11	83,80±16,21	4,55±0,87
LSD ₀₅			9,99 mm	12,02 mm	0,22	32,26 q	1,73 q

The results of the statistical analysis of biochemical parameters (Table 2) showed that, among the studied genotypes, the mean values were as follows: dry matter $5.48 \pm 0.44\%$, sugars $2.84 \pm 0.26\%$, extractive substances $4.37 \pm 0.42\%$, total acidity $0.37 \pm 0.03\%$, sugar-acid ratio 8.15 ± 0.98 , and nitrate content 119.14 ± 20.61 mg/kg. The LSD₀₅ values for the studied indicators were 0.88, 0.52, 0.84, 0.06 %, 1.95, and 41.01 mg/kg, respectively. At the upper 95 % confidence level, genotypes A-15 (6.63 %) and A-17 (7.28 %) differed significantly from the other genotypes, whereas at the lower confidence level, genotype A-29 (4.33 %) was distinct.

The dry matter content of the remaining 39 genotypes was within the confidence interval (4.65–6.15%). For sugar content, genotypes 394 (3.43%), A-24 (3.47%), A-12 (3.60%), A-8 (3.62%), A-15 (3.70%), and A-17 (4.28%) were distinguished at the upper 95% confidence level, whereas genotypes A-7 (1.0%), 296 (2.0%), and 401 (2.17%) differed at the lower confidence level. Thus, in the remaining 39 genotypes, the dry matter content was within the confidence interval (4.65–6.15%). For sugar content, at the upper confidence level, genotypes 394 (3.43%), A-24 (3.47%), A-12 (3.60%), A-8 (3.62%), A-15 (3.70%), and A-17

(4.28%) were distinguished, whereas at the lower confidence level, genotypes A-7 (1.0%), 296 (2.0%), and 401 (2.17%) differed. Regarding the content of extractive substances, at the upper confidence level, only genotype A-17 (5.46%) was distinguished, whereas at the lower confidence level, genotype A-7 (2.73%) differed. In the remaining genotypes, sugar and extractive contents were within the confidence intervals.

In terms of total acidity, the number of samples differing at the upper confidence level was relatively high. These included genotypes 86 (0.51%), 138 (0.45%), 283 (0.50%), 285 (0.46%), 296 (0.47%), A-1 (0.45%), A-7 (0.51%), A-10 (0.44%), A-14 (0.47%), A-27 (0.48%), and A-28 (0.45%). At the lower confidence level (below 0.31%), the differing genotypes included A-2 (0.28%), 417 (0.30%), 398 (0.23%), 395 (0.28%), 394 (0.25%), and 307 (0.30%).

Regarding the sugar-to-acid ratio, at the upper confidence level (above 10.10), the following genotypes differed: 394 (13.19), 385 (11.43), 398 (11.65), A-6 (10.38), A-8 (11.68), A-12 (11.25), A-15 (11.94), A-17 (13.38), and A-24 (10.52). At the lower confidence level (below 6.20), the distinct genotypes were A-27 (5.83), A-10 (5.75), A-7 (1.96), 296 (4.26), 285 (5.44), 283 (5.06), 140 (5.75), 138 (5.78), and 86 (4.51).

Comparative evaluation of the fruits of tomato genotypes grown in cocopeat under greenhouse conditions due to some biochemical indicators (average for 2023–2024)

№	Catalog sample of the VGRI	Names of the genotypes	Dry matter, %	Sugars, %	Extractive substances, %	Total acidity, %	$\frac{\text{Sugars}}{\text{Acidity}}$	Nitrates, mg/kg
1	86	Banovsha, registered variety, standard	5,25	2,30	4,34	0,51	4,51	80,3
2	138	Shalala, registered variety, standard	6,15	2,60	4,60	0,45	5,78	97,4
3	140	Pure line	4,65	2,30	3,79	0,40	5,75	80,6
4	283	Pure line	5,56	2,53	4,53	0,50	5,06	105,5
5	285	Pure line	5,43	2,50	4,48	0,46	5,44	107,5
6	296	Pure line	6,10	2,0	4,05	0,47	4,26	110,8
7	306	Pure line	5,40	2,50	4,26	0,33	7,58	154,5
8	307	Pure line	5,33	2,57	4,13	0,30	9,57	198,1
9	321	Pure line	5,53	2,50	4,17	0,33	7,58	140,9
10	343	Pure line	5,33	2,73	4,36	0,37	7,38	152,3
11	356	Pure line	5,63	2,50	4,57	0,31	8,07	105,3
12	393	Pure line	5,10	2,50	4,15	0,25	10,0	134,9
13	394	Sample selected from the variety Atlas	5,99	3,43	4,70	0,26	13,19	185,6
14	395	Pure line (New variety)	5,33	3,20	4,53	0,28	11,43	175,9
15	396	Pure line	5,38	2,85	4,72	0,36	7,92	136,3
16	398	Sample selected from the variety First Ladu	5,89	2,68	4,06	0,23	11,65	111,3
17	401	Pure line	5,88	2,17	4,99	0,33	8,79	107,3
18	415	Pure line	5,23	3,40	4,79	0,39	8,72	81,8
19	417	Pure line	5,28	2,50	4,15	0,30	7,23	140,9
20	462	Mulmuctap F ₁	5,70	3,30	4,90	0,38	8,68	160,9
21	A-1	(43x420) F ₁	5,20	3,20	4,91	0,45	7,11	154,3
22	A-2	(495x391) F ₁	5,23	2,78	4,21	0,28	9,93	152,5
23	A-3	(436x415) F ₁	5,30	3,30	4,43	0,38	8,68	81,0
24	A-5	(306x285) F ₁	5,68	2,80	4,09	0,42	6,67	75,8
25	A-6	(475x468) F ₁	5,73	3,32	4,69	0,32	10,38	83,0
26	A-7	(138x283) F ₁	5,08	1,0	2,73	0,51	1,96	76,0
27	A-8	(375x436) F ₁	6,08	3,62	4,90	0,31	11,68	31,1
28	A-9	(198x306) F ₁	5,15	2,37	4,06	0,36	6,58	71,5
29	A-10	(198x307) F ₁	5,18	2,53	3,87	0,44	5,75	61,6

30	A-12	(420x415) F ₁	5,65	3,60	5,0	0,32	11,25	109,0
31	A-14	(306x283) F ₁	5,15	2,03	4,31	0,47	6,45	119,0
32	A-15	(351x447) F ₁	6,63	3,70	4,99	0,31	11,94	56,0
33	A-17	(584x351) F ₁	7,28	4,28	5,46	0,32	11,38	74,2
34	A-18	(487x395) F ₁	5,58	3,0	4,34	0,33	9,09	176,0
35	A-20	(468x420) F ₁	4,83	2,80	4,06	0,36	7,78	104,6
36	A-24	(487x321) F ₁	5,63	3,47	4,57	0,33	10,52	89,8
37	A-25	(487x143) F ₁	5,03	3,0	4,26	0,38	7,90	104,6
38	A-26	(375x425) F ₁	5,23	3,25	4,51	0,34	9,56	202,9
39	A-27	(307x283) F ₁	5,05	2,80	4,05	0,48	5,83	110,4
40	A-28	(307x306) F ₁	5,18	2,70	4,15	0,45	6,44	110,8
41	A-29	(468x438) F ₁	4,33	2,50	3,77	0,38	6,58	110,5
42	A-30	(391x143) F ₁	4,83	2,73	3,38	0,34	8,03	117,5
Range of variation			4,33-7,28	1,0-4,28	2,73-5,46	0,23-0,51	1,96-13,38	56,0-13,38
$\bar{X} \pm S_{\bar{x}}$			5,48±0,44	2,84±0,26	4,37±0,42	0,37±0,03	8,15±0,98	119,14±20,61
LSD ₀₅			0,88 %	0,52 %	0,84 %	0,06 %	1,95	41,01 mg/kg

It is known that the sugar-to-acid ratio (or sugar-acid index) in tomato fruits should be at least 7 for optimal quality, especially when processing tomatoes for juice and paste. This ratio is an important indicator determining the taste quality of the fruits [Pikaleva A.S., 2018; Machulkina V.A. et al., 2014; Pavlov L.V. et al., 2011]. According to Pikaleva, as the sugar-to-acid index decreases, the quality of the tomato declines, and the taste of the resulting juice or paste deteriorates. In the study by Machulkina V.A. et al., the sugar-to-acid index ranged from 8.8 to 12.2, and they concluded that this ratio depends more on the biological characteristics of the genotype than on other factors. Nevertheless, the value of this ratio is also influenced by mineral nutrition and the storage conditions of the tomatoes.

In our previous studies, we noted that the content of toxic substances – nitrates – in tomato fruits depends on the biological characteristics of the genotypes, soil and climatic conditions, the level of mineral nutrition, the degree of ripeness, and other factors [Agayev F.N. et al., 2023; 2024; Allahverdiyev E.I. et al., 2020; Yusifov M.A., Agazade F.N., 2003]. The results of the present study showed that the nitrate content in tomato fruits averaged 119.14 ± 20.61 mg/kg, with a CV (Coefficient of Variation at 5% significance level) of

41.01 mg/kg. At the 95% confidence level, the genotypes with the highest nitrate content (above 160.15 mg/kg) were A-18 (176.0), A-26 (202.9), 307 (198.1), 394 (185.6), 395 (175.9), and 462 (160.9 mg/kg), whereas those with the lowest nitrate content (below 78.13 mg/kg) were A-5 (75.8), A-7 (76.0), A-9 (71.5), A-10 (61.6), A-17 (74.2), and A-15 (56.0 mg/kg).

As a result of the study, 10 tomato genotypes were selected based on a complex of biochemical characteristics and recommended for future selection according to quality (Table 3). In these selected samples, the dry matter content ranged from 5.65 to 7.28%, the sugar content from 2.68 to 4.28%, the extractives from 4.06 to 5.46%, total acidity from 0.23 to 0.38 %, the sugar-to-acid ratio from 7.38 to 13.38, and the nitrate content from 56.0 to 185.6 mg/kg.

It should be noted that, as in our previous studies, in the present study the content of toxic substances – nitrates in tomato fruits did not exceed the permissible limit established by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan for greenhouse-grown tomatoes (300 mg/kg) and was 1.48–5.36 times lower than this limit.

Tomato genotypes grown in cocopeat under greenhouse conditions, selected based on biochemical composition and recommended for breeding according to quality (average for 2023–2024)

No	Catalog sample of the VGRI	Names of the genotypes	Dry matter, %	Sugars, %	Extractive substances, %	Total acidity, %	Sugars Acidity	Nitrates, mg/kg
1	343	Pure line	5,98	2,73	4,36	0,37	7,38	152,3
2	394	Sample selected from the variety Atlas	5,99	3,43	4,70	0,26	13,19	185,6
3	398	Sample selected from the variety First Ladu	5,89	2,68	4,06	0,23	11,65	111,3
4	401	Pure line	5,88	3,17	4,99	0,33	8,79	107,3
5	462	Mulmuctap F ₁	5,70	3,30	4,90	0,38	8,68	160,9
6	A-6	(375x468)F ₁	5,73	3,32	4,69	0,32	10,38	83,0
7	A-8	(375x436)F ₁	6,08	3,62	4,90	0,36	11,68	90,1
8	A-12	(420x415)F ₁	5,65	3,60	5,0	0,32	11,25	109,0
9	A-15	(351x447)F ₁	6,63	3,70	4,99	0,31	11,94	56,0
10	A-17	(584x351)F ₁	7,28	4,28	5,46	0,32	13,38	74,2
Range of variation			5,65-7,28	2,68-4,28	4,06-5,46	0,23-0,38	7,38-13,38	56,0-185,6

Conclusion. Under Absheron conditions, the morphological and biochemical characteristics in the fruits of tomato genotypes cultivated on cocopeat in a greenhouse vary over a wide range. The mean values of fruit height, diameter, and moisture and dry mass were 48.49 ± 5.02 mm, 57.09 ± 6.04 mm, 83.80 ± 16.21 g, and 4.55 ± 0.87 g, respectively.

The mean values of the biochemical parameters were as follows: dry matter 5.48 ± 0.44 %; 0.88%, sugars 2.84 ± 0.26 %; 0.52%, extractive substances 4.37 ± 0.42 %; 0.84%, total acidity 0.37 ± 0.03 %; 0.06%, sugar-acid ratio 8.15 ± 0.98 1.95, and nitrates 119.14 ± 20.61 mg/kg; 41.01 mg/kg, respectively.

As a result of the study, ten cultivars – 343, 394, 398, 401, 462, A-6, A-8, A-12, A-15, and A-17 were selected based on a set of biochemical parameters and are used as valuable donors for selection aimed at high quality.

The genotypes A-15, A-17, A-6, and A-8 among the studied hybrids exhibit extremely low nitrate levels (56.0–90.1 mg/kg, 3.33–5.36 times below the permissible limit), making them valuable parental forms for breeding aimed at producing environmentally safe products.

Among the studied hybrids, the genotypes A-15, A-17, A-6, and A-8 exhibit extremely low nitrate levels (56.0–90.1 mg/kg, 3.33–5.36 times below the permissible limit), making them valuable parental forms for breeding aimed at producing environmentally safe products.

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